

Study on Effect of Rotor Sail on Seakeeping and Manoeuvring of Ships

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Abstract. In this study, the effects of rotor sails on seakeeping and manoeuvring performance are investigated. While previous studies have focused on the forces acting on standalone rotor sail under uniform flow through CFD or experimental approaches, this research aims to evaluate the influence of rotor sails installed on ships, specifically on ship motions and manoeuvring dynamics. To achieve this, an efficient computational model for rotor sail is required to accurately calculate the forces generated by rotor sails, addressing their impact on ship dynamics in a wide range of inflow conditions, such as the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) wind profile. To address this need, a rotor sail model is developed using a nonlinear lifting line theory, which is further enhanced with a circulation distribution based on the Fourier sine series. This integrated approach ensures efficient and accurate force calculations under diverse inflow conditions, making it particularly suitable for assessing ship performance in various environmental conditions. The proposed rotor sail model is incorporated into the time-domain seakeeping and manoeuvring coupled simulation program, WISH-MANEUVER, enabling the evaluation of rotor sail effects on ship motions and manoeuvring in waves. The forces generated by rotor sails are included in the manoeuvring equations of motion as external forces, while the aerodynamic damping method is employed to reflect their influence in seakeeping simulations. Using this program, simulations were conducted on the KVLCC2 hull form equipped with rotor sails under various environmental conditions. The results revealed that the influence of rotor sails on seakeeping is relatively small, whereas their impact on manoeuvring is highly dependent on wind direction, affecting rudder behavior and engine power demand. These findings provide detailed insights into the effect of the aerodynamic forces by rotor sails on ship dynamics, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of their seakeeping and manoeuvring performance across a wide range of operational scenarios.

Keywords: *Wind-assisted propulsion, Rotor sail, Nonlinear lifting-line method, Seakeeping, Manoeuvring*

1 Introduction

In response to the tightening regulations on ships' carbon emissions, such as the Energy Efficiency Design Index (EEDI) [1] and the Energy Efficiency Existing Ship Index (EEXI) [2] introduced by the International Maritime Organization (IMO), there has been growing interest in wind-assisted propulsion systems (WAPS) such as rotor sail as shown in **Figure 1**. These systems are capable of generating auxiliary propulsive forces and thereby reducing the power consumption of the main engine. Among the various technologies, rotor sails have attracted significant attention due to their ability to generate high propulsive forces through the Magnus effect and their feasibility for retrofitting onto existing vessels.

While numerous studies have investigated rotor sails, most of them have focused on investigating the lift and drag coefficients generated by a standalone rotor under simplified conditions. This is primarily due to the complex and nonlinear nature of the aerodynamic force involved, which makes accurate force estimation challenging. In contrast, the influence of rotor sails installed on the ships, especially their effects on seakeeping and manoeuvring performance, remains relatively unexplored.

Several studies have attempted to integrate rotor sail forces into ship manoeuvring simulation [3][4] or seakeeping simulation [5] using simplified modeling

Figure 1. Example of rotor sail application (© HD Hyundai)

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techniques. In these approaches, the aerodynamic forces are estimated using lift and drag coefficients obtained from experimental data or CFD analysis. These forces are integrated along the rotor height using a strip-theory-based method to calculate the total forces and moments acting on the ship. However, such methods fall short of accurately capturing the three-dimensional force distribution along the rotor height and neglect complex interaction effects between multiple rotors. Although Tillig et al. [3] considered the interactions between the rotors, the interaction effects were approximated using two-dimensional potential vortex methods, which could be insufficient for certain conditions.

Accurate prediction of the aerodynamic forces and moments generated by rotor sails under realistic conditions would ideally require high-fidelity CFD simulations or experimental studies. However, the high computational cost and time requirements of these approaches make them impractical for investigating the seakeeping or manoeuvring performance of rotor sail-installed ships.

Recent work by Schot et al. [6] proposed the application of the nonlinear lifting line theory, originally developed by Phillips et al. [7], to wing sail and rotor sail modeling. This approach allows for efficient and sufficiently accurate modeling of the aerodynamic forces. Moreover, it has been extended to include interaction effects in rotor sail systems based on the lifting line formulation, as demonstrated by Malmek et al. [8][9] in their study on wing sail interaction. Their results, which were validated against wind tunnel experimental data and CFD simulations and demonstrated good agreement and strong potential for practical applications.

Despite these advancements, the majority of lifting line-based models have so far been developed under the assumption of uniform inflow conditions. However, ships operating in real seaways are subject to wind profiles that follow an atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) distribution, resulting in twisted and sheared inflow conditions.

In this study, the advanced rotor sail model based on the nonlinear lifting line theory is developed, incorporating a circulation distribution based on Fourier sine series and accounting for twisted wake vortices induced by the non-uniform inflow condition. This enables the model to operate effectively under non-uniform flow conditions such as ABL wind profiles, providing an accurate and efficient method to evaluate aerodynamic loads on rotor sails under realistic environmental conditions.

This developed rotor sail model is integrated into WISH-MANEUVER, a time-domain seakeeping and manoeuvring coupled simulation program. In this program, the aerodynamic forces generated by the rotor sails are introduced into the manoeuvring equations of motion as external forces. For the seakeeping analysis, the unsteady aerodynamic forces from ship motion are decomposed, and only the unsteady components are considered in the seakeeping problem.

To demonstrate the applicability of the proposed modeling approach, a case study is conducted on the KVLCC2 hull form equipped with rotor sails. The study investigates the impact of rotor sail forces on both seakeeping and manoeuvring performance under various environmental conditions.

2 Rotor Sail Force Modeling

2.1 Nonlinear lifting line theory

Unlike the classical lifting line theory, which extends two-dimensional (2D) potential theory-based airfoil characteristics into three dimensions (3D) by accounting for the influence of downwash generated by wake vortex filaments, the nonlinear lifting line theory proposed by Phillips et al. [7] incorporates the nonlinear characteristics of 2D lift coefficients. This is achieved by utilizing pre-obtained 2D nonlinear lift coefficient data from experiments or CFD. The theory assumes that the spanwise lift distribution, which results from the circulation distribution of a finite-span lifting body, must match the 2D lift generated at each sectional airfoil, corresponding to the local inflow velocity and its associated lift coefficients. This leads to the following nonlinear equation:

$$\rho \Gamma(z) |V_{local}(z) \times dl| = \frac{1}{2} \rho |V_{\infty}(z)|^2 C_l dA \quad (1)$$

Where ρ is the density of air, V_{∞} is the inflow velocity, V_{local} is the local velocity, Γ is the circulation distribution and C_l is the 2D lift coefficient. In this equation, the left-hand side represents the lift magnitude derived from the lifting line theory based on the local velocity and circulation, while the right-hand side corresponds to the lift calculated from the pre-obtained 2D lift coefficient (C_l). For airfoils, the C_l is typically a function of Reynolds number and angle of attack.

However, for the rotor sail considered in this study, the lift magnitude is not dependent on the angle of attack, but rather on the spin ratio (SR). Moreover, in the case of rotor sails, the differential vortex length vector dl always

acts in the vertical direction (rotating axis of the rotor sail; z -axis), and the differential area dA is determined by the constant cylinder diameter. Considering these geometric and aerodynamic characteristics, the nonlinear equation for rotor sail can be reformulated as follows:

$$2|V_{local}(z)|\Gamma(z) = D|V_{\infty}(z)|^2 \cdot C_l \left(SR(z) = \frac{\omega \cdot D}{2|V_{local}(z)|} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where D is the diameter of the circular cylinder and ω is its rotational speed. In this nonlinear equation, the circulation distribution is the target variable to be solved. In this study, the nonlinear 2D lift coefficient data of the rotor sail were obtained by interpolating CFD results from Schot et al.[6]. The local velocity, which depends on the circulation distribution according to the lifting line theory, can be express for a standalone rotor sail as follows:

$$V_{local}(z) = V_{\infty}(z) + w_i(z) \quad (3)$$

where w_i denotes the downwash velocity induced by the lifting line theory.

2.2 Wake vortex modeling and downwash velocity

While previous studies that apply the lifting line theory have primarily focused on calculating the circulation distribution under uniform inflow conditions, rotor sails installed on actual operating ships are typically subject to non-uniform inflow profiles. This discrepancy arises because the wind field encountered by a ship is more accurately represented by an atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) profile, in which wind speed varies with height. When this wind shear is considered, the apparent wind profile experienced by the rotor sail becomes twisted along the rotor height due to the relative motion of the ship, as shown in **Figure 2(a) and 2(b)**.

Figure 2. Wind velocity profiles and vortex filament alignment

This is in contrast to the uniform flow assumption adopted in most prior studies, and consequently, the direction of the wake vortices in the lifting line formulation must be modified. To appropriately account for such non-uniform inflow conditions, this study assumes that the wake vortex filaments at each height along the rotor are aligned with the local inflow direction (see **Figure 2(c)**). To define the direction of the wake vortices, velocity twist function $\alpha(z)$ and $\beta(z)$ were introduced.

$$\frac{V_{\infty}(z)}{|V_{\infty}(z)|} = \beta(z) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{i}} + \alpha(z) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{j}} \quad (4)$$

To ensure stable numerical convergence of the nonlinear lifting line equations under such asymmetric inflow conditions, the circulation was represented using a Fourier sine series-based distribution, while the velocity twist functions were transformed using a cosine series.

$$\Gamma \left(z = \frac{L}{2} \cos \theta \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} G_n \sin n\theta \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha(\theta) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} A_m \cos m\theta, \quad \beta(\theta) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} B_m \cos m\theta \quad (6)$$

where L is the rotor sail height, with the z -axis placed at its midpoint. The downwash induced by wake vortices is the computed based on the Biot-Savart law.

$$\mathbf{w}_i(z) = w_{i,x} \hat{\mathbf{i}} + w_{i,y} \hat{\mathbf{j}} \quad (7)$$

$$w_{i,x} = \frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \frac{\Gamma'(\zeta) \alpha(\zeta)}{z - \zeta} d\zeta, \quad w_{i,y} = -\frac{1}{4\pi} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \frac{\Gamma'(\zeta) \beta(\zeta)}{z - \zeta} d\zeta \quad (8)$$

By introducing a change of variables and substituting the Fourier sine and cosine series representations of the circulation distribution and the velocity twist functions, respectively, the above integral can be evaluated analytically using the Glauert integral.

$$w_{i,x} \left(z = \frac{L}{2} \cos \theta \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} G_n \cdot I_n^x(\theta), \quad w_{i,y} \left(z = \frac{L}{2} \cos \theta \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} G_n \cdot I_n^y(\theta) \quad (9)$$

$$I_n^x(\theta) = \frac{n}{4L} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \left[A_m \cdot \left(\frac{\sin(n+m)\theta}{\sin \theta} + \frac{\sin|n-m|\theta}{\sin \theta} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

$$I_n^y(\theta) = -\frac{n}{4L} \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \left[B_m \cdot \left(\frac{\sin(n+m)\theta}{\sin \theta} + \frac{\sin|n-m|\theta}{\sin \theta} \right) \right]$$

2.3 Aerodynamic interaction modeling

When multiple rotor sails are present, aerodynamic interactions between them must be considered. Several previous studies have addressed such interactions using strip theory [3] or lifting line theory [6][8][9], and experimental investigation has also been reported [10]. In studies based on lifting line theory, the influence of vortex filaments from multiple lifting lines is incorporated into the local velocity to account for interaction effects. In the present study, a similar approach is adopted to model the interaction between the rotor sails. When considering aerodynamic interactions among N_{Rotor} rotor sails, the local inflow velocity at i -th rotor is can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{V}_{local,i}(z) = \mathbf{V}_{\infty}(z) + \mathbf{w}_{ii}(z) + \sum_{j \neq i}^{N_{Rotor}} \mathbf{w}_{ij}(z) \quad (11)$$

Here, \mathbf{w}_{ii} represents the self-induced downwash velocity from the rotor itself, as described in **Section 2.2**, while \mathbf{w}_{ij} represents the velocity induced by the j -th rotor's vortex filaments. Unlike the single-rotor case, aerodynamic interactions among multiple rotors involve both wake (free) vortices and bound vortices.

$$\mathbf{w}_{ij}(z) = w_{f-ij,x}(z) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{i}} + w_{f-ij,y}(z) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{j}} + w_{b-ij,x}(z) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{i}} + w_{b-ij,y}(z) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{j}} \quad (12)$$

Where subscripts f and b denote free (wake) and bound vortices, respectively. The induced velocities from each component are evaluated using the Biot-Savart law and substitution integrals, resulting in the following integral expressions.

$$w_{f-ij,x} \left(z = \frac{L}{2} \cos \theta \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} G_n^j \cdot I_{n,f-ij}^x(\theta), \quad w_{f-ij,y} \left(z = \frac{L}{2} \cos \theta \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} G_n^j \cdot I_{n,f-ij}^y(\theta) \quad (13)$$

$$w_{b-ij,x} \left(z = \frac{L}{2} \cos \theta \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} G_n^j \cdot I_{n,b-ij}^x(\theta), \quad w_{b-ij,y} \left(z = \frac{L}{2} \cos \theta \right) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} G_n^j \cdot I_{n,b-ij}^y(\theta) \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{n,f-ij}^x(\theta) &= \frac{-n}{2\pi L} \int_0^\pi \frac{\cos(n\varphi) \alpha(\varphi) (\cos\theta - \cos\varphi)}{r'(\varphi, \theta) \{r'(\varphi, \theta) - \beta(\varphi) \Delta x' - \alpha(\varphi) \Delta y'\}} d\varphi \\
I_{n,f-ij}^y(\theta) &= \frac{n}{2\pi L} \int_0^\pi \frac{\cos(n\varphi) \beta(\varphi) (\cos\theta - \cos\varphi)}{r'(\varphi, \theta) \{r'(\varphi, \theta) - \beta(\varphi) \Delta x' - \alpha(\varphi) \Delta y'\}} d\varphi
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

$$I_{n,b-ij}^x(\theta) = \frac{-\Delta y'}{2\pi L_j} \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin(n\varphi) \sin\varphi}{r'(\varphi, \theta)^3} d\varphi, \quad I_{n,b-ij}^y(\theta) = \frac{\Delta x'}{2\pi L_j} \int_0^\pi \frac{\sin(n\varphi) \sin\varphi}{r'(\varphi, \theta)^3} d\varphi \tag{16}$$

Where $\Delta x' = \frac{\Delta x}{L/2}$, $\Delta y' = \frac{\Delta y}{L/2}$, $r'(\varphi, \theta) = \sqrt{\Delta x'^2 + \Delta y'^2 + (\cos\theta - \cos\varphi)^2}$, and here, Δx and Δy represents the

distance between the rotor sails along the x -axis and y -axis, respectively.

Since these integrals generally do not have closed-form solutions, they were evaluated using adaptive numerical integration through QAGS subroutine in QUADPACK library, which employs a globally adaptive 21-points Gauss-Kronrod quadrature method. [11]

2.4 Iterative computational scheme

To solve the nonlinear lifting line equation, the Newton-Raphson method is employed. The rotor sail is first uniformly discretized in the θ -domain into N_{seg} segments, and the local velocity at each segment is expressed accordingly:

$$\mathbf{V}_{local,i}(z_k) = \mathbf{V}_{\infty,i}(z_k) + \sum_{j=1}^{N_{Rotor}} \sum_{n=1}^{N_{Seg}} \mathbf{G}_n^j \cdot \mathbf{H}_{n,ij}(z_k) \tag{17}$$

$$\mathbf{H}_{n,ij}(z_k) = \begin{cases} \{I_{n,f-ij}^x(\theta_k) + I_{n,b-ij}^x(\theta_k)\} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{i}} + \{I_{n,f-ij}^y(\theta_k) + I_{n,b-ij}^y(\theta_k)\} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{j}} & (i \neq j) \\ I_n^x \cdot \hat{\mathbf{i}} + I_n^y \cdot \hat{\mathbf{j}} & (i = j) \end{cases} \tag{18}$$

For iterative computation, the residual (\mathbf{R}_s) and the Jacobian matrix (\mathbf{J}_{st}) are derived with the following variable substitutions:

$$s = N_{Seg}(i-1) + k, \quad t = N_{Seg}(j-1) + n \tag{19}$$

$$\mathbf{R}_s = 2|\mathbf{V}_{\infty,s} + \mathbf{w}_s| \Gamma_s - D|\mathbf{V}_{\infty,s}|^2 C_l(SR_s) \tag{20}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{J}_{st} &= \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_s}{\partial \mathbf{G}_t} = 2 \frac{\partial |\mathbf{V}_{local,s}|}{\partial \mathbf{G}_t} \Gamma_s + 2|\mathbf{V}_{local,s}| \frac{\partial \Gamma_s}{\partial \mathbf{G}_t} - D_s |\mathbf{V}_{\infty,s}|^2 \frac{\partial C_l(SR_s)}{\partial SR_s} \cdot \frac{\partial SR_s}{\partial \mathbf{G}_t} \\
\frac{\partial |\mathbf{V}_{local,s}|}{\partial \mathbf{G}_t} &= \frac{\mathbf{V}_{local,s} \cdot \mathbf{H}_{st}}{|\mathbf{V}_{local,s}|}, \quad \frac{\partial \Gamma_s}{\partial \mathbf{G}_t} = \begin{cases} \sin(n\theta_k) & (i = j) \\ 0 & (i \neq j) \end{cases}, \quad \frac{\partial SR_s}{\partial \mathbf{G}_t} = -SR_s \cdot \frac{\mathbf{V}_{local,s} \cdot \mathbf{H}_{st}}{|\mathbf{V}_{local,s}|^2}
\end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Where $\mathbf{V}_{local,s} = \mathbf{V}_{\infty,s} + \sum_{t=1}^{N_{Total}} \mathbf{H}_{st} \mathbf{G}_t$, $N_{Total} = N_{Seg} \times N_{Rotor}$.

The iterative procedure for determining the circulation distribution over each rotor sail proceeds as follows. First, the inflow condition along the rotor height is evaluated to compute the apparent wind profile. From this, the velocity twist function is obtained and transformed into cosine series. The aerodynamic influence matrix \mathbf{H}_{st} , which accounts for both downwash and rotor interaction effects, is then constructed through numerical integration. An initial guess for the circulation distribution is provided using an elliptic distribution. At each iteration step, the local velocity is updated based on the current circulation values and \mathbf{H}_{st} , and the resulting residual and Jacobian matrix are used to compute the next update. This process is repeated until convergence is achieved (see **Figure 3**).

Figure 3. Flow chart of rotor sail model based on the nonlinear lifting line theory

Using the circulation distribution obtained through the iterative procedure, the lift and induced drag distributions acting on the rotor sails can be computed. The viscous drag component is estimated based on pre-obtained 2D drag coefficient (C_d) data and the final local velocity at each segment. In this study, as with the 2D lift coefficient, the drag coefficient data were obtained by interpolating CFD results provided by Schot et al. [6]. The total aerodynamic forces acting on the rotor sails are then evaluated by integrating the lift, induced drag, and viscous drag components along the vertical axis of the rotor.

3 Coupled Analysis of Rotor Sail and Ship Motion

3.1 Ship hydrodynamic solver: WISH-MANEUVER

WISH-MANEUVER is an in-house simulation program developed at Seoul National University for the coupled analysis of seakeeping and manoeuvring motion. The program consists of a time-domain seakeeping module based on the 3D Rankine panel method and a manoeuvring module based on the MMG (Manoeuvring Modeling Group) model.

In WISH-MANEUVER, the coupling between seakeeping and manoeuvring is handled by taking into account that the characteristic time scale of manoeuvring motion is significantly larger than that of seakeeping motion. Accordingly, from the perspective of high-frequency seakeeping motion, the manoeuvring motion is assumed to be quasi-steady. At each predefined coupling interval, the results from the manoeuvring simulation are treated as steady inflow condition for the seakeeping module, and the boundary value problem of seakeeping problem is redefined.

The seakeeping module computes linear wave forces and second-order wave drift forces, which are then incorporated in the equations of motion in MMG-based manoeuvring module. Through this method, the two modules are solved independently within each coupling interval, allowing for a computationally efficient direct coupling of seakeeping and manoeuvring simulations.

The theoretical background of the WISH-MANEUVER program and further details on the seakeeping-manoeuving coupling strategy can be found in Seo et al. [12] and Lee et al. [13][14].

3.2 Coupling of rotor sail and manoeuvring solver

As described above, the wind field acting on a ship operating in real sea conditions follows an atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) profile. This wind distribution corresponds to the true wind speed (TWS) profile, defined in a fixed global coordinate system O -XYZ.

$$TWS(Z) = V_0 \left(\frac{Z}{Z_0} \right)^\alpha \quad (22)$$

Here, Z is the vertical height from the waterline, Z_0 is the reference height (typically 10m), V_0 is the wind speed at the reference height, and α is the Hellmann exponent.

The apparent wind velocity profile represents the actual inflow velocity experienced by the rotor sails and is defined in the ship-fixed coordinate system as the relative wind. While the apparent wind can vary in direction depending on the ship's position and motion, this study considers only the velocity components perpendicular to

the vertical axis of the rotor sail, neglecting components aligned with it. These perpendicular components are used to define the effective inflow condition for the rotor sail model.

The aerodynamic coupling of the rotor sail in the manoeuvring simulation is implemented as follows. First, the apparent wind velocity profile, which is affected by the ship's motion, is applied as the inflow condition to the rotor sail model. Based on this inflow, the nonlinear lifting line theory is used to compute the aerodynamic forces and moments generated by the rotor sail with respect to the manoeuvring center. These loads are then incorporated into the 4-DoF manoeuvring equations of motion, which can be written as follows:

Figure 4. Coordinate definition for manoeuvring problem

$$\begin{cases} m(\dot{u} - vr) = X_H + X_R + X_P + X_{linear} + X_{wave} + X_{wind} + X_{Rotor} \\ m(\dot{v} + ur) = Y_H + Y_R + Y_{linear} + Y_{wave} + Y_{wind} + Y_{Rotor} \\ I_{xx}\dot{p} = K_H + K_R + K_{linear} + K_{wave} + K_{wind} + K_{Rotor} \\ I_{zz}\dot{r} = N_H + N_R + N_{linear} + N_{wave} + N_{wind} + N_{Rotor} \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

In this formulation, m , I_{xx} , and I_{zz} denote the ship's mass and the moments of inertia about the x -axis and z -axis, respectively. X and Y represent surge and sway forces, while K and N denote roll and yaw moments. The subscripts H , P , and R indicate hydrodynamic contributions from hull, propeller, and rudder, respectively. Subscripts $linear$ and $wave$ refer to linear wave forces and second-order wave drift force computed by the seakeeping module. $wind$ and $Rotor$ denote the aerodynamic forces acting on the hull and those generated by the rotor sail, respectively.

The wind forces acting on the hull are estimated from the empirical formula proposed by Fujiwara et al. [15]. Further details on the component-wise formulation of the MMG model and the treatment of environmental forces in WISH-MANEUVER can also be found in the aforementioned study [13][14].

3.3 Coupling of rotor sail and seakeeping solver

To account for the influence of rotor sails on the ship's seakeeping motion, an aerodynamic damping force model is employed. In the seakeeping module, the manoeuvring motion is treated as a steady baseline condition. Therefore, the relative inflow velocity experienced by the rotor sail must be calculated by combining both the manoeuvring and seakeeping motions and positions. The resulting apparent wind velocity profile is then used to evaluate the time-dependent aerodynamic forces and moments acting on the rotor sail.

Figure 5. Example of rotor sail force decomposition considering seakeeping motion

However, these computed forces and moments inherently include steady-state components that have already been incorporated into the manoeuvring equations of motion. Directly applying them to the seakeeping equations would result in double-counting of the steady forces. To avoid this, the total aerodynamic load is decomposed into steady and unsteady components, and only the unsteady portion is applied to the seakeeping equations (see **Figure 5**). This decomposition forms the basis of the aerodynamic damping force model.

$$\delta \mathbf{F}_{Rotor}(t) = \mathbf{F}_{Rotor}(t) - \bar{\mathbf{F}}_{Rotor} \quad (24)$$

For this end, the rotor sail forces and moments are first computed using both seakeeping and manoeuvring motion. ($\mathbf{F}_{Rotor}(t)$) Then, the steady component ($\bar{\mathbf{F}}_{Rotor}$), which is previously used in the manoeuvring module, is recomputed under the same conditions. The difference between the total and steady components yields the unsteady aerodynamic force ($\delta \mathbf{F}_{Rotor}(t)$), which is incorporated into the 6-DoF seakeeping equations of motion.

$$[M] \{\ddot{\xi}\} = \{\mathbf{F}_{F.K.}\} + \{\mathbf{F}_{Res.}\} + \{\mathbf{F}_{H.D.}\} + \{\delta \mathbf{F}_{Rotor}\} \quad (25)$$

In this formulation, $[M]$ denotes the inertia matrix of the ship, and $\{\xi\}$ represents the 6-DoF rigid-body motion. $\mathbf{F}_{F.K.}$ and $\mathbf{F}_{Res.}$ correspond to the Froude-Krylov force and restoring force, respectively, while $\mathbf{F}_{H.D.}$ represents the hydrodynamic forces due to disturbed wave and ship motion. A more detailed explanation of the individual force components in the seakeeping equation can be found in earlier referenced literature [13][14].

4 Numerical results and discussion

4.1 Validation of rotor sail model

Prior to integrating the rotor sail model into the ship simulation, the proposed modeling approach was validated against the wind tunnel experiments conducted under various conditions by Bordogna et al. [10]. Although the present model is designed to handle non-uniform inflow conditions, publicly available experimental or CFD data for such cases are lacking. Therefore, the validation was performed under uniform inflow conditions only.

The rotor sail geometry used in the present simulations matched the experimental setup, with a diameter of 0.6m and a height of 1.5m. To account for the effect of end plates, a virtual extension at the top of the rotor was applied during the circulation distribution computation, following the method of Schot et al. [6], with the extended length set to 10% of the total height. In the final force integration, this virtual end plate region was excluded, and only the actual rotor region was considered.

As the first step, the aerodynamic performance of a single rotor sail was validated. The simulation was conducted under uniform flow conditions corresponding to a Reynolds number of 7.0×10^4 , as in the experiment. The rotational speed varied according to the spin ratio.

Figure 6. Aerodynamic coefficients of single rotor sail

Figure 6 presents the comparison of three-dimensional lift (C_L) and drag (C_D) coefficients obtained from the model and the experimental data. The present model slightly overestimates lift across the range but shows good agreement in overall trends for both lift and drag.

In the next step, aerodynamic interactions between multiple rotor sails were investigated through simulations of a two rotor sails configuration replicating the experimental setup. The two rotors, referred to as Rotor A and Rotor B, had identical geometry as in the single-rotor case, as shown in **Figure 7**. Two separation distances between the rotors (d) were examined: 3 and 7.5 times the rotor diameter. The inflow condition corresponded to a Reynolds number of 7.0×10^4 , and the spin ratio was fixed at 2.0 for both rotors.

The relative positioning of the rotors varied depending on the wind direction. At a wind angle of 0° , Rotor A was placed upstream, directly facing the wind, while Rotor B was located downstream.

Figure 7. Configuration of two rotor sails in tandem

Figure 8. Aerodynamic coefficients of two rotor sails in tandem ($d/D = 3.0$) (left) Rotor A (right) Rotor B

Figure 8 presents the comparison of lift (red) and drag (blue) coefficients for Rotor A and Rotor B as functions of wind direction, under the condition where the spacing between the rotors is three times the rotor diameter. The experimental results are shown alongside the predictions from the present model. For reference, dashed line indicates the calculated aerodynamic coefficients for a single rotor sail under the same condition.

The model overestimates lift, consistent with the trend observed in the single-rotor case. However, in regions where aerodynamic interactions are most significant, specifically when the wake vortex from Rotor B approaches Rotor A, the model captures both the magnitude and trend of the experimental results with reasonable accuracy. For the drag coefficients, the simulation results show good agreement with the experimental data.

Figure 9. Aerodynamic coefficients of two rotor sails in tandem ($d/D = 7.5$) (left) Rotor A (right) Rotor B

The results for the case with a rotor spacing of 7.5 times the diameter are shown in **Figure 9**. Compared to the previous case with closer spacing, the aerodynamic interaction effects were significantly reduced, except in wind directions where one rotor was positioned close to the wake region of the other. Although the present model tends to overpredict lift coefficients due to its inherent overestimation in the single-rotor case, the overall trends remain consistent with the experimental observations.

4.2 Ship models and rotor sail conditions

To analyze the influence of rotor sails on ship motions, simulations were conducted using the KVLCC2 hull form. The principal dimensions of the KVLCC2 used in the simulations are summarized in **Table 1**. Four rotor sails were arranged in a single line along the longitudinal axis of the ship, as shown in **Figure 10**, and their specifications are in **Table 2**.

Table 1. Principal dimensions of KVLCC2

Designations	KVLCC2
LBP, L_{BP} [m]	320.0
Beam, B [m]	58.0
Draft, T [m]	20.8
Displacement volume, ∇ [m ³]	312,622
Block coefficients, C_B [-]	0.810
Radius of gyration, k_{xx}/B [-]	0.4
Radius of gyration, k_{yy}/L , k_{zz}/L [-]	0.25
Design Froude number, F_r	0.142 (15.5 [knots])

Table 2. Parameters of rotor sail

Designations	Rotor sail
Number of rotors	4
Installed position from midship [m]	(± 50 [m], 0[m]), (± 100 [m], 0[m])
Diameter, D [m]	5.0
Height, L [m]	30.0
End plate diameter, D_e [m]	10.0
Virtual end plate extension [%]	10.0
Rotational speed ω [rpm]	180.0

Figure 10. Rotor sail configuration on KVLCC2

4.3 Seakeeping – Rotor sail coupled simulation results

The influence of rotor sails on seakeeping performance was evaluated through simulations conducted under the environmental conditions listed in Table 3. The Hellmann exponent, which characterizes the vertical wind speed profile, was set to 0.27, following the value used in the study by Tillig et al. [3]. The ship’s forward speed was fixed at its design value ($F_r = 0.142$) throughout the seakeeping simulations.

Table 3. Environmental conditions of seakeeping simulations

Wind condition	
True wind speed (at $z_0 = 10$ m), V_0 [m/s]	12
Hellmann exponent, α [-]	0.27
True wind angle, χ_{wind} [°]	90
Wave condition	
Wave amplitude, A_{wave} [m]	1.0, 3.0
Wave heading, χ_{wave} [°]	90
Wavelength, λ / L_{BP} [-]	0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4, 1.6, 2.0

Figure 11. RAOs of KVLCC2 with and without rotor sail under different wave amplitudes.

Figure 11 presents the response amplitude operators (RAOs) results of the KVLCC2 obtained from the coupled seakeeping – rotor sail simulations. The black solid line represents the bare hull configuration without rotor sails, while the blue and green dashed lines correspond to the RAO results with rotor sails installed, under wave amplitudes of 1m and 3m, respectively.

The results indicate that the influence of rotor sails on the seakeeping behavior of the KVLCC2 is negligible. This is attributed to the fact that the unsteady components of the forces and moments generated by the rotor sails are significantly smaller in magnitude compared to other terms in the seakeeping equations of motion and therefore do not have a meaningful impact on the overall ship response.

4.4 Manoeuvring – Rotor sail coupled simulation results

The influence of rotor sails on manoeuvring performance was investigated using straight-line course-keeping simulations under the environmental conditions summarized in **Table 4**. The Hellmann exponent was set to 0.27, consistent with the value used in the seakeeping analysis. Simulations were conducted under calm sea conditions without waves and at a constant forward speed, in order to isolate the aerodynamic effects of the rotor sails.

Table 4. Environmental conditions of manoeuvring simulations

Wind condition	
True wind speed (at $z_0 = 10$ m), V_0 [m/s]	12
Hellmann exponent, α [-]	0.27
True wind angle, χ_{wind} [°]	0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, 180

Among the 4-DoF in manoeuvring motion, roll was excluded from the simulation, since its effect is negligible for large tankers such as the KVLCC2. As a result, a 3-DoF simulation was performed. Course-keeping was controlled using a PD controller acting on a rudder angle, based on the built-in algorithm of WISH-MANEUVER. A detailed description of this control logic can be found in Lee et al. [14].

The effects of rotor sails under different wind directions were analyzed using two performance indicators. The first is the thrust ratio, defined as the thrust generated by the rotor sails divided by the total thrust required to maintain the constant forward speed. The second is the power ratio, defined as the sum of the delivered power to the propeller and the rotor sail operating power, normalized by the power required without rotor sails.

$$\text{Thrust ratio} = \frac{X_{Rotor}}{X_P + X_{Rotor}} \quad (26)$$

$$\text{Power ratio} = \frac{P_{P, w/ Rotor sail} + P_{Rotor}}{P_{P, w/o Rotor sail}} \quad (27)$$

The delivered power ($P_{P, w/ Rotor sail}$, $P_{P, w/o Rotor sail}$) was estimated from the propeller torque corresponding to the rotational speed used in the manoeuvring simulations, with the influence of manoeuvring-related forces taken into account, including hull hydrodynamic forces, rudder forces, propeller forces, and wind forces. The rotor sail operating power was calculated through a strip-theory-based integration using the local inflow velocity and the aerodynamic torque, which was derived from the power coefficient. This coefficient was expressed as a polynomial function of the spin ratio, obtained via regression analysis. In this study, the coefficient values proposed by Tillig et al. [3] were adopted.

$$C_{Power}(SR) = \frac{P_{Rotor}}{0.5\rho AV_\infty^3} = 0.0234 \cdot SR - 0.0168 \cdot SR^2 + 0.0143 \cdot SR^3 - 0.0004 \cdot SR^4 + 0.0001 \cdot SR^5 \quad (28)$$

Figure 12 presents polar diagrams of the thrust ratio and power ratio as functions of the true wind angle. Under the current simulation conditions, when the wind angle exceeds 150° relative to the stern, the aerodynamic force generated by the rotor sails acts against the direction of motion, resulting in increased engine power demand. In other words, the rotor sails contribute additional resistance in this range, leading to a reduction in overall energy efficiency. In contrast, the highest thrust contribution and power-saving effect are observed when the wind angle

is approximately 60° . These results indicate that the operational benefit of rotor sails strongly depends on the inflow wind angle, and their use should be carefully evaluated according to inflow conditions.

The influence of the rotor sails was also reflected in the rudder input required to maintain a straight-line manoeuvre. As the wind direction changed, the lateral aerodynamic forces generated by the rotor sails varied, inducing yaw moments that had to be compensated by the rudder. **Figure 13** illustrates the rudder angles required for course keeping at different true wind angles. Notably, at wind angles of 120° and 150° , rudder deflections exceeding 3° were necessary to maintain a straight course. These results indicate that rotor sails can introduce significant side forces depending on the wind direction, which in turn affect the steering performance of the vessel even during nominally straight-line operation.

Figure 12. (Left) Thrust ratio (Right) Power ratio with respect to the true wind angle χ_{wind}

Figure 13. Required rudder angle for course keeping with respect to the true wind angle χ_{wind}

5 Conclusion

This study presented a rotor sail force model based on nonlinear lifting line theory and applied it to seakeeping and manoeuvring simulations of a KVLCC2 tanker. The model accounts for non-uniform inflow conditions, aerodynamic interactions among multiple rotor sails, and employs a Newton–Raphson–based numerical solution scheme. Validation against experimental data for both isolated and interacting rotor sail configurations showed reasonable agreement in lift and drag characteristics.

In seakeeping simulations, the unsteady aerodynamic forces generated by the rotor sails had negligible influence on ship motion due to their relatively small magnitude compared to other governing forces. In contrast, the manoeuvring simulations revealed a strong dependence of rotor sail performance on the wind angle. When the true wind angle approached approximately 60° off the stern, the sails provided notable thrust and energy-saving benefits. Conversely, at wind angles exceeding 150° , the aerodynamic forces opposed the ship's motion, leading

to increased engine power demand. The influence of rotor sails was also observed in rudder behavior. Depending on the wind direction, significant lateral forces required rudder deflections exceeding 3° to maintain a straight course, even under steady forward operation.

These results highlight that the effectiveness of rotor sails is highly dependent on wind direction, with both beneficial and adverse effects observed under different conditions. Their implementation therefore requires operational strategies that account for prevailing wind environments. Furthermore, the integrated simulation framework developed in this study provides a practical tool for evaluating the dynamic impact of rotor sails on ship performance. While the current work focused on developing a practical evaluation method, future work may involve validating the model under more diverse conditions as needed in specific design applications.

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